

An unsurprising emergence of logarithmic sensing technologies

Stuart Bingham*

June 28, 2024

Keywords — ratio, logarithm, fold change, visualization, quasi-logarithmic function, **gene expression analysis**, variance stabilization, compandor, **density analysis**, edge detection, quasi-logarithmic Laplacian filter, **cluster analysis**, location quotient, visual salience, **term frequency analysis**, Jaccard similarity, **network analysis**, scholarly influence, **constructal law**, design evolution

Abstract

Large ratios displayed in finite areas call for bounded distortion. This note introduces a quasi-logarithmic function that achieves bounded distortion, gives meaning to ratios involving zero, and finds utility in logarithmic sensing technologies tailored to tasks of visualization, signal processing, and data science. Designs of logarithmic sensors appear poised to evolve and emerge more broadly across a range of data-driven disciplines.

Introduction

The diverse utility of logarithmic transformation in estimating constant percentage growth rates, remediating skewed distributions, and balancing visualizations of ratios suggests a utility untapped, beyond conventional applications. Methods of visualizing ratios point to a bounded variant of the logarithmic function, and five examples hint at a range of applications; the margins of this note invite readers to make a few sketches and *imagine* a broader range of possibilities for analysis of ratios involving zero.

Layouts on the printed page of the binary tree of nonnegative rational numbers known as the Stern-Brocot tree [1] begin with placement of the label $\mathbf{0/1}$ at the left margin, placement of the label $\mathbf{1/0}$ (“infinity in lowest terms” [2]) at the right margin, and placement of the *primal mediant* $\mathbf{1/1}$ (the root of the Stern-Brocot tree) midway between the extremes $\mathbf{0/1}$ and $\mathbf{1/0}$. Intermediate ratios known as *mediants*,

$$\frac{a}{b} < \frac{a+c}{b+d} < \frac{c}{d},$$

fill nodes of the Stern-Brocot tree with rational numbers. Nodes at the second level hold children of the root, $\mathbf{1/2}$ on the left and $\mathbf{2/1}$ on the right; nodes at the third level hold $\mathbf{1/3}$, $\mathbf{2/3}$, $\mathbf{3/2}$, and $\mathbf{3/1}$. Construction proceeds in this way to fill the Stern-Brocot tree with mediants enumerating the nonnegative rationals in lowest terms.

*sbingham3142@pm.me

In such layouts of the Stern-Brocot tree, rationals less than one occupy an interval of unit length to the left of the primal mediant, and their reciprocals (which, if plotted in proportion to distance from primal mediant, would demand an interval of infinite length) squeeze into an interval of unit length on the right. Bar charts of ratios call for a similar distortion of lengths to avoid misinterpretation; in one example of a design required to convey the same message independently of roles given to terms of a ratio, Evans et al. [3] assign bars of equal length to a ratio and its reciprocal.

Functions that produce such distortions of lengths satisfy the condition

$$|f(x) - 1| = |f(1/x) - 1|;$$

the piecewise (linear for small x , hyperbolic for large x) smooth function

$$f(x) = \begin{cases} x & (0 \leq x \leq 1) \\ 2 - 1/x & (x > 1) \end{cases}$$

satisfies this condition, leaving values in the unit interval untouched and squeezing values greater than one into an interval of unit length [4]. A unit shift downward produces the quasi-logarithmic function

$$qlog(x) \triangleq \begin{cases} (x - 1)/1 & (0 \leq x \leq 1) \\ (x - 1)/x & (x > 1), \end{cases}$$

its piecewise construction concealed in the equivalent definition

$$qlog(x) \triangleq \frac{x - 1}{\max\{1, x\}} \quad (x \geq 0).$$

Unlike the logarithmic function, $qlog$ maps zero to -1 ; like the logarithmic function, $qlog$ maps a value and its reciprocal to quasilogos of equal magnitude and opposite sign:

$$qlog(1/x) = -qlog(x) \quad (x > 0);$$

large values map to positive quasilogos and small values map to negative quasilogos. Leading terms of the infinite series [5]

$$log(x) = \frac{x-1}{1} - \frac{1}{2}\left(\frac{x-1}{1}\right)^2 + \frac{1}{3}\left(\frac{x-1}{1}\right)^3 - \frac{1}{4}\left(\frac{x-1}{1}\right)^4 + \dots \quad (0 < x \leq 2)$$

$$log(x) = \frac{x-1}{x} + \frac{1}{2}\left(\frac{x-1}{x}\right)^2 + \frac{1}{3}\left(\frac{x-1}{x}\right)^3 + \dots \quad (x > 1/2)$$

constitute the logarithmic essence of $qlog$. Counts of consecutive nines, as in

$$qlog(10^{\pm n}) = \pm 0.\bar{9}^n$$

easily give order-of-magnitude estimates of large *and* small antiquasilogos.

Substitution of p/q for x calls into play the terms of a ratio to redefine $qlog$ as

$$qlog(p, q) \triangleq \frac{p - q}{\max\{p, q\}} \quad (p \geq 0, q > 0);$$

two additional modifications equip

$$qlog(p, q) \triangleq \begin{cases} -1 & (0 = p < q) \\ +1 & (0 = q < p) \\ p/q - 1 & (0 < p < q) \\ 1 - q/p & (0 < q < p) \\ 0 & (0 < p = q) \\ NaN & (0 = p = q) \end{cases}$$

to map infinite ratios to one in agreement with

$$\lim_{x \rightarrow \infty} qlog(x) = 1$$

and to propagate a NaN in lieu of attempting to divide zero by zero. This definition of $qlog$ gives meaning to *all* ratios of nonnegative integers; in the following examples, the ratio of zero to zero demands no effort of division to convey meaningful interpretations of *no contrast* and *nothing to compare*.

Logarithmic sensors in biological [6] and biomimetic realms emit finite signals and respond equally to equivalent ratios of strong and weak signals. The quasi-logarithmic function $qlog$ operates over an infinite dynamic range,

$$qlog(ap, aq) = qlog(p, q) \quad (a > 0),$$

emitting identical signals on consumption of equivalent ratios, and responding with the same intensity in ascent and descent of a gradient:

$$qlog(q, p) = -qlog(p, q).$$

These behaviors equip $qlog$ with the biomimetic agency to *sense* transitions between extreme, intermediate, and non-numeric states; the following five examples introduce designs of quasi-logarithmic sensors, evolved to facilitate exploration of phenomena that freely present ratios of nonnegative terms for analysis.

Gene expression analysis

Convergence of semiconductor microlithography and gene sequencing technologies late in the twentieth century produced the DNA microarray and as biology morphed into a data-driven discipline, analysts of gene-expression microarray data found measurements of luminous intensities lacking in the mean-independent variances necessary for conventional methods of statistical inference. In 2002, Blythe Durbin-Johnson et al. [7] found the inverse hyperbolic sine to stabilize variances of luminous intensities acquired from gene-expression microarrays.

The inverse hyperbolic sine stabilizes variance by expanding and compressing a signal in a manner reminiscent of a *compandor* [8], an analog device known in 1934 to suppress noise in radio telephone signals by *compressing* and *expanding* a signal. The graph of the inverse hyperbolic sine $y = \operatorname{arcsinh}(x)$ near the origin of the (x, y)

plane resembles the graph of the identity function $y=x$; this local resemblance to the identity function cooperates with the identity

$$\operatorname{arcsinh}(x) \stackrel{[5]}{\cong} \log(x + \sqrt{x^2 + 1})$$

to reveal a quasi-exponential function bound to the oblique asymptote $y=2x$,

$$\operatorname{expo}(x) \triangleq x + \sqrt{x^2 + 1}.$$

Expression of $\operatorname{arcsinh}$ as the composition of the logarithmic function after the oblique exponential function expo suggests utility in the composition of $qlog$ after expo ,

$$qlex(p, q) \triangleq \begin{cases} +1 & (p>0, q=0) \\ qlog(\operatorname{expo}(p/q)) & (p\geq 0, q>0) \\ NaN & (p=0, q=0), \end{cases}$$

a composition more aggressive than $\operatorname{arcsinh}$ at suppressing large ratios.

Density analysis

Appropriately quantized, many discrete univariate distributions of density (frequency of occurrence) exhibit episodic (temporal) or modal (spatial) structure marked by noticeable transitions between segments of high and low activity or frequency; extreme cases exhibit lengthy segments void of activity or frequency. Changes in sign of the output of a Laplacian-of-Gaussian (LoG) filter, viewed as changes in concavity of a smooth approximation, tend to reveal edges true to the structure of such distributions.

Cursory explorations of episodic and modal distributions suggest that the *quasi-logarithmic Laplacian filter*

$$qlap(x_{i-1}, x_i, x_{i+1}) \triangleq qlog(qlex(x_{i+1}, x_i), qlex(x_i, x_{i-1}))$$

tends to sense edges having greater contrast than edges sensed by a three-tap LoG. Replacement of $qlog$ with the logarithmic function and $qlex$ with the identity function reduces $qlap$ to a Laplacian filter on a log-transformed stream of data, incapable of filtering streams that emit zeros or negative values.

Magnitudes of $qlog$ -transformed ratios of adjacent segments' densities associate contrast to edges, and extreme values of contrast reveal segments void of activity or frequency. Edgesets constitute run-length-encoded summaries of distributions; edges assigned over a range of scales form hierarchical structures of some utility in forensic investigations of prior quantization, inadequate sampling, and other pathologies.

Cluster analysis

Within collections of literature, publications sharing terminology and interests gather in clusters and at larger scales, in clusters of clusters. Analyses of such clusters quantify relative abundance of an attribute (institutional affiliation, membership in a tagged subset, etc.) with ratios of ratios known as *location quotients*,

$$\frac{n_{ij}/N_i}{n_j/N} = \frac{n_{ij}/n_j}{N_i/N},$$

involving the terms

n_{ij}		number of publications in cluster i having attribute j
n_j		number of publications in collection having attribute j
N_i		number of publications in cluster i
N		number of publications in a collection.

Tabular summaries of location quotients, highlighted by relative abundance of an attribute, exhibit signatures of highlighting in the same way that fluorescent fragments of DNA bound to sites of a DNA microarray exhibit signatures of fluorescence. However, as distributions of location quotients tend to exhibit skewness, signatures of fluorescence written across tabular summaries of location quotients can call for some clever coaxing to maximize visual salience. Prior transformation of location quotients with a power function, as in

$$qlog(x^\alpha) = \frac{x^\alpha - 1}{\max\{1, x^\alpha\}} \quad (x \geq 0, \alpha > 0),$$

permits manipulation of contrast; choices of $\alpha \gg 1$ tend to classify location quotients as either large or small [9].

Term frequency analysis

Quasilogs of term frequency ratios facilitate fully-detailed comparisons of two texts: terms absent from one text and present in the other produce extreme quasilogs, and terms common to both produce intermediate quasilogs. In one example, Lt. D. David Bourland, Jr. presents two translations of an excerpt from a work by Machiavelli, one from Latin to English and the other, from English to a subset of English void of the verb *to be* in all of its forms, *E-Prime* [10]. Quasilogs of term frequency ratios from these two translations facilitate production of an ordered list of terms having verbs introduced in translation to E-prime near the top and inflections of *to be* (*be, been, is, was, am, were, ...*) near the bottom; in this example, verbs near the top of the list give substance to the claim that the practice of writing in E-prime promotes usage of the active voice.

Knowledge of the number of term frequency ratios having intermediate-valued quasilogs facilitates computation of Jaccard similarity of two termsets,

$$J(A,B) = \frac{|A \cap B|}{|A \cup B|},$$

a measure easily modified to involve a pair of multisets [1]. Frequency distributions of quasilogs of term frequency ratios offer informative comparisons of multisets: identical multisets exhibit a single spike at zero; disjoint multisets exhibit no positive frequencies other than a pair at ± 1 ; a multiset strictly contained exhibits a positive frequency at exactly one extremum. Anomalous pairs of multisets drawn from a set of multisets exhibit visually distinct frequency distributions of quasilogs of term frequency ratios.

Network analysis

Attribution flows through citation networks, into the past; *influence* flows through citation networks, toward the future. A citation network holds three overlapping collections of literature in the vicinity of a focal work: set F (containing *foundational* works cited by the focal work), set D (containing *derivative* works that cite the focal work), and set C (containing works bibliographically *coupled* to the focal work by citation of literature foundational to the focal work). Evans et al. [3] enlist a measure of technological change due to Funk et al. [11],

$$\frac{n_i - n_j}{n_i + n_j + n_k} \Big|_{n_k=0} = \frac{n_i - n_j}{n_i + n_j} \Big|_{n_j>0} = \frac{n_i/n_j - 1}{n_i/n_j + 1} \stackrel{[5]}{\approx} \log \sqrt{\frac{n_i}{n_j}},$$

involving elements of a partition of the union of derivative and coupled collections,

$$\begin{aligned} n_i &= |D-C| \\ n_j &= |D \cap C| \\ n_k &= |C-D|, \end{aligned}$$

to place focal works on a scale from -1 (deemed developing) to +1 (deemed disruptive). Quasilogs of ratios of uncoupled derivative works to coupled derivative works,

$$qlog(|D-C|, |D \cap C|),$$

compare flows of scholarly influence from foundational works to derivative works: in the case $|D-C|=0$, all influence flows through the focal work; in the case $|D \cap C|=0$, all influence flows past the focal work.

A citation network centered on the focal work of Durbin-Johnson et al. [7] holds five foundational works, 1,528 coupled works, and 275 derivative works; the positive quasilog of the ratio of $|D-C|=178$ uncoupled derivative works to $|D \cap C|=97$ coupled derivative works highlights this focal work as a source of influence; its signature of fluorescence, written across clusters of termwise-similar documents tagged by membership in foundational, derivative, and coupled collections, reveals 97 coupled derivative works on a narrow range of analytical methods, and 178 uncoupled derivative works reflecting an emergence of high-throughput gene sequencing technologies across a broad range of biological and medical applications.

Concluding remarks

Distortions, committed to fit graphical layouts into the page and onto the screen, have motivated the design of a bounded quasi-logarithmic function that gives meaning to ratios involving zero and manifests the agency to sense transitions between states. The quasi-logarithmic Laplacian filter introduced in this note has evolved to reveal structure in batches and streams of numerical data and other designs have evolved, almost as if drawn, to facilitate delivery of insightful results across a range of applications in the data-driven disciplines. A broader emergence of logarithmic sensing technologies across the data-driven disciplines would come as no surprise, given the natural tendency of networks — including information delivery networks — to manifest a semblance of vitality, play on the art of the possible, and pave new avenues of delivery. The constructal law of design evolution [12] expresses this natural tendency. Now equipped with additional evidence, the constructal law hints at further growth in applications of logarithmic sensing technologies across the data-driven disciplines.

Annotated bibliography and endnotes

[12] Professor Adrian Bejan presents constructal theory in *Street network theory of organization in nature* (Journal of Advanced Transportation (June 1996) Vol. 30, No. 2, pp. 85-107). José L. Lage, Ren Anderson, and others recap the discovery of the constructal law by Professor Bejan, in *Professor Adrian Bejan on his 60th birthday* (International Journal of Heat and Mass Transfer 51 (2008) pp. 5759-5761).

[11] Russell J. Funk and Jason Owen-Smith outline a network-analytical approach to the study of technological change in *A dynamic network measure of technological change* (Management Science, Vol. 63, No. 3, March 2017, pp. 791-817).

[10] E-Prime enlivens technical exposition and activates creative thinking. Associate Professor of Linguistics and United States Navy Lieutenant D. David Bourland, Jr. authored TO BE OR NOT TO BE: *E-Prime as a Tool for Critical Thinking* (appearing in *To Be or Not: An E-Prime Anthology* compiled by D. David Bourland, Jr. and Paul Dennithorne Johnston; International Society for General Semantics, 1991). In this work, Lt. Bourland exhibits a translation from Latin to English of the excerpt from Machiavelli, surrounded by whitespace and fully displayed on one left page, together with a translation of the excerpt from English to E-Prime, similarly displayed on the facing page. This two-up display gives sequential access to discrepancies; lists ordered by quasilogs of term frequency ratios, on the other hand, simultaneously reveal detailed and large-scale structures of commonality.

[9] Another composition involving $qlog$ and the power function (not known to facilitate analysis of ratios involving zero),

$$f(x) = \begin{cases} qlog((qlog^{-1}(\sin(x)))^\alpha) & (x \neq \pi/2 \pm 2n\pi, n=0,1,\dots) \\ 1 & (x = \pi/2 \pm 2n\pi, n=0,1,\dots), \end{cases}$$

operates as a waveform generator to produce a sine wave ($\alpha=1$), a triangular wave ($\alpha=1/2$), approximations to a square wave ($\alpha \gg 1$), and trains of alternating, impulsive cusps ($0 < \alpha \ll 1$).

[8] The abstract of the work by R.C. Mathes and S.B. Wright, *The Compandor — An Aid Against Static in Radio Telephony* (The Bell System Technical Journal, July, 1934) introduces this analog design as “an automatic device which compresses the range of useful signal energy variations at the transmitting end and expands the range to normal at the receiving end, thus improving the speech-to-noise ratio.”

[7] Blythe Durbin-Johnson, Johanna S. Hardin, Douglas M. Hawkins, and David M. Rocke derive a variance-stabilizing property of the inverse hyperbolic sine in their influential work, *A variance-stabilizing transformation for gene-expression microarray data*, (Bioinformatics, Volume 18, Issue supplement 1, July 2002, pp. S105-S110).

[6] Biological sensory systems at different levels of organization exhibit the logarithmic behavior of fold-change detection. Oren Shoval and co-authors describe several such biological systems and their logarithmic properties in *Fold-change detection and scalar symmetry of sensory input fields* (Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences, September 7, 2010, Volume 107, Number 36, pp. 15995-16000).

[5] *Tables of Integrals and Other Mathematical Data*, 4/e, compiled by Herbert Bristol Dwight (New York, The Macmillan Company, 1961) includes the infinite series

$$\begin{aligned} \log(x) &= \frac{x-1}{1} - \frac{1}{2}\left(\frac{x-1}{1}\right)^2 + \frac{1}{3}\left(\frac{x-1}{1}\right)^3 - \frac{1}{4}\left(\frac{x-1}{1}\right)^4 + \dots & (0 < x \leq 2) \\ \log(x) &= \frac{x-1}{x} + \frac{1}{2}\left(\frac{x-1}{x}\right)^2 + \frac{1}{3}\left(\frac{x-1}{x}\right)^3 + \dots & (x > 1/2) \\ \log(\sqrt{x}) &= \frac{x-1}{x+1} + \frac{1}{3}\left(\frac{x-1}{x+1}\right)^3 + \frac{1}{5}\left(\frac{x-1}{x+1}\right)^5 + \dots & (x > 0) \end{aligned}$$

in entries 601.5, 601.6, and 601.7; entry 602.1 catalogs the identity (mentioned in this note, in the example on gene expression analysis) involving the inverse hyperbolic sine, the logarithmic function, and a quasi-exponential function.

[4] The piecewise (hyperbolic for small x , linear for large x) unbounded candidate

$$f(x) = \frac{x-1}{\min\{1, x\}} \quad (x > 0)$$

(made of pieces discarded, during construction of $q\log$), and the bounded candidate

$$f(x) = \frac{x-1}{x+1} \quad (x \geq 0),$$

also satisfy the condition $|f(x)-1| = |f(1/x)-1|$; substitution of p/q for x reveals the latter to involve nonnegative terms of a ratio simply as

$$f(p, q) = \begin{cases} (p-q)/(p+q) & (p \geq 0, q \geq 0, p+q > 0) \\ NaN & (p=0, q=0). \end{cases}$$

[3] Reciprocals of large ratios give balance to the bar chart in Figure 1c of the letter by Lingfei Wu, Dashun Wang, and James A. Evans, *Large teams develop and small teams disrupt science and technology*, (Nature **556**, 21 February 2019). In this letter, Evans et al. enlist a measure of technological change introduced by Funk et al. [11] to assess flows of scholarly influence through citation networks.

[2] Authors Ronald L. Graham, Donald Ervin Knuth, and Oren Patashnik give light-hearted and substantive treatment to the Stern-Brocot tree in *Concrete Mathematics: A Foundation for Computer Science*, 2/e (Addison-Wesley Professional, 1994); the remark reproduced in the left margin of this page originally appeared, courtesy of a playful student editor, as graffiti in the left margin of a page in an early edition of *Concrete Mathematics*, next to an illustration of the Stern-Brocot tree.

[1] This note takes a cue or two (annotation of bibliographic references, for one) from one foundational work of Donald E. Knuth, THE ART OF COMPUTER PROGRAMMING, 2/e, Volume 2/*Seminumerical Algorithms*, (Addison-Wesley Publishing Company, 1981). Intermediate-level exercise 19 [M23] of §4.5.3 presents the multiset, a set permitted to contain multiple copies of its elements, equivalent to a set equipped with a mapping into the nonnegative integers. (Unions of multisets map to maximum multiplicities; intersections of multisets map to minimum multiplicities.) Intermediate-level exercise 40 [M28] of §4.6.3 presents the Stern-Pierce tree, now known as the Stern-Brocot tree.

I guess 1/0
is “infinity in
lowest terms.”